

Novel Fractional Integral Identities and Inequalities with Atangana-Baleanu Operators

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XÜLASƏ Son illərdə kəsrvi analiz sahəsində bir çox yeni inteqral operatorların təqdim edilməsi ilə əhəmiyyətli irəliləyişlər yaşanmışdır. Bu irəliləyişlər arasında Atangana-Baleanu kəsrvi inteqral operatoru xüsusilə diqqət çəkir. Bu operator ilk dəfə 2016-cı ildə Atangana və Baleanu tərəfindən təyin edilmişdir və kəsrvi kalkulyus sahəsində mühüm maraq doğurur. Bu məqalədə, Atangana-Baleanu kəsrvi inteqral operatorundan istifadə edərək yeni bir eynilik təqdim edirik. Xüsusilə, iki dəfə törəmələyə bilən konveks funksiyalar və Godunova-Levin funksiyaları üçün bir sıra innovativ kəsrvi inteqral bərabərsizliklər türetilmişdir. Bu yeni əldə edilən bərabərsizliklər, kəsrvi inteqral operatorlarının xüsusiyyətləri və tətbiqləri haqqında yeni baxışlar təqdim edir və onların nəzəri çərçivəsini əhəmiyyətli dərəcədə irəlilətməkdədir. Daha ətraflı şəkildə təqdim edilən nəticələr geniş bir funksiyalar sinfi üçün potensial tətbiqlərə malikdir və kəsrvi analiz sahəsində müxtəlif tətbiqlərə təsir göstərə bilər. Bu iş, yeni bərabərsizliklərin ətraflı araşdırılması ilə kəsrvi inteqral operatorlarının nəzəri çərçivəsini genişləndirmək və tədqiqatçılar üçün dəyərli bir mənbə təqdim etmək məqsədini güdür. Tapıntılar, kəsrvi analizdə qabaqcıl metodlar və yanaşmalar inkişaf etdirmək istəyən araşdırmaçılara ilham vermək və bu dinamik sahənin inkişafına töhfə vermək niyyətindədir.

Açar sözlər: Kəsrvi Bərabərsizliklər, Atangana-Baleanu İnteqral Operatoru, Konveks Funksiya, (s, m) Godunova-Levin Funksiyaları.

ABSTRACT In recent years, the field of fractional analysis has experienced significant advancements with the introduction of numerous new integral operators. Among these advancements, the Atangana-Baleanu fractional integral operator has emerged as a particularly notable contribution. This operator was first defined by Atangana and Baleanu in 2016 and has since become a central topic of interest within the domain of fractional calculus. In this paper, we introduce a novel identity that leverages the Atangana-Baleanu fractional integral operator to establish new theoretical results. Specifically, we derive a series of innovative fractional integral inequalities that apply to twice differentiable convex functions as well as Godunova-Levin functions. These newly derived inequalities offer fresh insights into the properties and applications of fractional integral operators, significantly advancing the current understanding of their theoretical

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underpinnings. Moreover, the results presented in this study have far-reaching implications for a broad class of functions, potentially influencing various applications within the field of fractional analysis. By providing a detailed exploration of these new inequalities, this paper aims to enhance the theoretical framework of fractional integral operators and offer valuable references for researchers. The findings are expected to inspire further research and development of advanced methods and approaches in fractional analysis, thus contributing to the ongoing evolution of this dynamic area of mathematical study.

Key words: Fractional Inequalities, Atangana-Baleanu integral operator, Convex Function, (s, m) Godunova-Levin Functions

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics, with a history as ancient as human civilization itself, stands as an indispensable tool for both pure and applied sciences. It not only illuminates the path to articulating complex problems but also provides the essential means to address and solve them. In its quest to achieve these objectives, mathematics employs a rich array of concepts and delves deeply into their intricate interrelationships. By defining various spaces and establishing algebraic structures upon these spaces, mathematics constructs frameworks that profoundly enhance our comprehension of the natural world and contribute significantly to multiple dimensions of human endeavor. Among these fundamental mathematical constructs, the notion of a function occupies a central and enduring role. Over time, scholars have invested considerable effort in exploring new classes of functions and in the systematic classification of function spaces. A particularly noteworthy class of functions that has emerged from these scholarly pursuits is that of convex functions. These functions are distinguished by their unique and well-defined properties, which facilitate their application across a broad spectrum of fields, including statistics, inequality theory, convex programming, and numerical analysis. Formally, a convex function can be defined as follows:

Let I be an interval in R . Then $f : I \rightarrow R, \emptyset \neq I \subseteq R$ is said to be convex if

$$f(ta + (1 - t)b) \leq tf(a) + (1 - t)f(b)$$

for all $a, b \in I$ and $t \in [0, 1]$.

This introduction serves as the preamble to our investigation into fractional Hermite-Hadamard type inequalities within the context of convex functions. Our exploration will focus on the application and extension of these inequalities, aiming to contribute valuable

insights and advancements to the field. By scrutinizing the behavior of fractional Hermite-Hadamard inequalities in the realm of convex functions, this study aspires to provide a deeper understanding and potentially novel results that will benefit both theoretical research and practical applications in mathematics. The Hermite-Hadamard inequality can be defined as follows:

Let $f: I \subseteq R \rightarrow R$ be a convex mapping defined on the interval I of real numbers and $a, b \in I$, with $a < b$. The following double inequalities statement:

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \leq \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2}$$

The double inequality described above is recognized in the academic literature as the Hermite-Hadamard inequality for convex functions. This inequality, which plays a pivotal role in the field of integral inequalities, has garnered significant attention from researchers. To provide a broader context and deeper insights into the realm of convexity and integral inequalities from various perspectives, to provide more information related to convexity and integral inequalities in different directions, see the papers [17], [4], [18], [2], [6].

METHODS

Definition 1 ([1]). A function $f: I \rightarrow R$ is said to be Godunova-Levin function, if

$$f(ta + (1-t)b) \leq \frac{f(a)}{t} + \frac{f(b)}{1-t}, \forall x, y \in I, t \in (0,1).$$

Definition 2 ([19]). A function $f: I \rightarrow R$ is said to be (s, m) -Godunova-Levin functions of first kind or $f \in Q_{(s,m)}^1$, if $\forall s, m \in (0, 1]$, we have

$$f(ta + m(1-t)b) \leq \frac{f(a)}{t^s} + m \frac{f(b)}{(1-t^s)}, \forall x, y \in I, t \in (0,1).$$

It is obvious that for $s = 0, m = 1$, (s, m) -Godunova-Levin functions of second kind reduces to P-functions. If $s = 1, m = 1$, it then reduces to Godunova-Levin functions. For $m = 1$, we have the definition of s -Godunova-Levin function of second kind introduced and studied by Dragomir [7, 8].

Although fractional analysis has been known since ancient times, it has recently gained significant traction in the fields of mathematical analysis and applied mathematics. What initially began as an exploration into the existence of solutions for differential

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equations with fractional orders has evolved into a multifaceted journey, marked by the development of numerous derivative and integral operators.

Over time, researchers have introduced fractional-order derivative and integral operators to propose more effective solutions for physical phenomena. This has led to the emergence of novel operators with general and robust kernels. These advancements have enriched both the field of mathematics and applied sciences, providing a diverse set of operators distinguished by their kernel structures, which vary in terms of locality and singularity. Additionally, these developments have given rise to generalized operators with memory effect properties.

The initial inquiry into the effects of fractional orders in differential equations has grown into a broader pursuit: understanding physical phenomena and identifying the most effective fractional operators for practical solutions to real-world problems.

In the following sections, we will present several pioneering fractional derivative and integral operators. These operators have not only advanced the field of fractional analysis but have also proven effective in various research areas. They have become essential tools for researchers across multiple domains. For further information on fractional analysis, please refer to the papers [3,5], [9-11], [21,22]

We will remember the Caputo-Fabrizio derivative operators. Also, we would like to note that the functions belong to Hilbert spaces denoted by $H^1(0, \theta_2)$

Definition 3 ([12]). Let $f \in H^1(0, \theta_2), \theta_2 > \theta_1, \alpha \in [0, 1]$ then the definition of the new Caputo fractional derivative is

$${}^{CF}D^\alpha f(x) = \frac{M(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \int_{k_1}^{x_1} f'(s) \exp\left[-\frac{\alpha}{(1-\alpha)}\right] ds,$$

where $M(\alpha)$ is normalization function.

Depending on this interesting fractional derivative operator, the authors have defined the Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integral operator as follows.

Definition 4 ([13]). Let $f \in H^1(0, \theta_2), \theta_2 > \theta_1, \alpha \in [0, 1]$ then the definition of the left and right side of Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integral is

$${}^{CF}I_\alpha f(x) = \frac{(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)} f(x) + \frac{\alpha}{B(\alpha)} \int_{\theta_1}^x f(y) dy,$$

and

$${}^{CF}I_{\theta_2}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{(1 - \alpha)}{B(\alpha)} f(x) + \frac{\alpha}{B(\alpha)} \int_x^{\theta_2} f(y) dy,$$

where $B(\alpha)$ is the normalization function

The Caputo-Fabrizio fractional derivative, which is used in dynamical systems, physical phenomena, disease models, and many other fields, is a highly functional operator by definition, but has a deficiency in terms of not meeting the initial conditions in the special case $\alpha = 1$. The improvement to eliminate this deficiency has been provided by the new derivative operator developed by Atangana-Baleanu, which has versions in the sense of Caputo and Riemann. In the sequel of this paper, we will denote the normalization function with $B(\alpha)$ with the same properties with the $M(\alpha)$ which is defined in Caputo-Fabrizio definition. (See [15,16])

The associated fractional integral operator has been defined by Atangana-Baleanu as follows.

Definition 5 ([14, 20]). The fractional integral associate to the new fractional derivative with nonlocal kernel of a function as defined:

$$\frac{{}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha \{f(x)\}}{2} = \frac{(1 - \alpha)}{B(\alpha)} f(x) + \frac{\alpha}{B(\alpha)} \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b f(x)(b - x)^{\alpha-1} dx.$$

Abdeljawad and Baleanu introduced the right hand side of integral operator as follows: the right fractional new integral with ML kernel of order $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is defined by

$${}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha \{f(x)\} = \frac{(1 - \alpha)}{B(\alpha)} f(x) + \frac{\alpha}{B(\alpha)} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f(x)(x - a)^{\alpha-1} dx$$

$B(\alpha)$ is the normalization function.

RESULTS

In this section, we give an identity which use to assist us for proving our results as follows:

Lemma 1. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow R$ be twice diferentiable function on (a, b) with $a < b$. If $f'' \in L[a, b]$

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$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{{}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\}} + {}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\} - \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)} \right] \\ & = \frac{(b-\alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \left[\int_0^1 t^{\alpha+1} f'' \left(t \frac{a+b}{2} + (1-t)a \right) dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_0^1 (1-t)^{\alpha+1} f'' \left(tb + (1-t) \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt \right] \end{aligned}$$

Where $\alpha \in [0,1]$, $B(\alpha)$ is the normalization function and $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is gamma function.

Proof. By using integration by parts for K_1 and K_2 , we have

$$\begin{aligned} K_1 + K_2 &= \int_0^1 t^{\alpha+1} f'' \left(t \frac{a+b}{2} + (1-t)a \right) dt \\ & \quad + \int_0^1 (1-t)^{\alpha+1} f'' \left(tb + (1-t) \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt. \end{aligned}$$

By using integration, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 K_1 &= \int_0^1 t^{\alpha+1} f'' \left(t \frac{a+b}{2} + (1-t)a \right) dt = \frac{t^{\alpha+1} 2f' \left(t \frac{a+b}{2} + (1-t)a \right)}{b-a} \\
 &\quad - 2 \int_0^1 \frac{2f' \left(t \frac{a+b}{2} + (1-t)a \right)}{b-a} (\alpha+1)t^\alpha dt \\
 &= \frac{2}{b-a} f' \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \\
 &\quad - \frac{2(\alpha+1)}{b-a} \left[\frac{2}{b-a} f' \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) - \frac{2(\alpha+1)}{b-a} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{2\alpha}{b-a} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f(x) \cdot \left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a} \right)^{(\alpha+1)} dx \right] \\
 &= \frac{2}{b-a} f' \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \\
 &\quad - \frac{2(\alpha+1)}{b-a} \left[\frac{2}{b-a} f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) - \frac{2^{\alpha+1}\alpha}{(b-a)^{\alpha+1}} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f(x)(x-a)^{\alpha-1} dx \right] \\
 &= \frac{2}{b-a} f' \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) - \frac{4(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^2} f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \\
 &\quad + \frac{2^{\alpha+1}\alpha(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha+1}} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f(x)(x-a)^{\alpha-1} dx
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, by using integration, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 K_2 &= \int_0^1 (1-t)^{\alpha+1} f'' \left(tb + (1-t) \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt \\
 &= -\frac{2}{b-a} f' \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + \frac{4(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^2} f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \\
 &\quad + \frac{2^{\alpha+1}\alpha(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha+1}} \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b f(x)(b-x)^{\alpha-1} dx
 \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying both sides of identity by $\frac{(b-a)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)}$ ($K_1 + K_2$).

Using the definition of Atangana-Baleanu fractional integral operators, we get,

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$$\frac{(b - \alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha + 1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha). \Gamma(\alpha)} (K_1 + K_2) = \left[\frac{{}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\}} + {}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\} - \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{B(\alpha)} \right].$$

Thus, The proof of lemma is done.

Theorem 1. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow R$ be twice diferentiable function on (a, b) with $a < b$. If $f'' \in L[a, b]$. If f'' is a convex function, we have the following inequality for Atangana-Baleanu fractional integral operators

$$\left| \frac{{}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\}} + {}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\} - \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{B(\alpha)} \right| \leq \frac{2}{\alpha + 3} \left| f'' \left(\frac{a + b}{2} \right) \right| + \frac{1}{(\alpha + 2)(\alpha + 3)} (|f''(a)| + |f''(b)|),$$

where $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, $B(\alpha)$ is the normalization function and $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is gamma function.

Proof. By using Lemma 1, we can write

$$\left| \frac{{}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\}} + {}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\} - \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{B(\alpha)} \right| \leq \frac{(b - \alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha + 1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha). \Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^1 t^{\alpha+1} \left| f'' \left(t \frac{a + b}{2} + (1 - t)a \right) \right| dt + \int_0^1 (1 - t)^{\alpha+1} \left| f'' \left(tb + (1 - t) \frac{a + b}{2} \right) \right| dt$$

By using convexity of $|f''|$, we get

$$\left| \frac{{}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\}} + {}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\} - \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{B(\alpha)} \right| \leq \int_0^1 t^{\alpha+1} \left(t \left| f'' \left(\frac{a + b}{2} \right) \right| + (1 - t) |f''(a)| \right) dt + \int_0^1 (1 - t)^{\alpha+1} \left(t |f''(b)| + (1 - t) \left| f'' \left(\frac{a + b}{2} \right) \right| \right) dt$$

By computing the above integrals, we obtain

$$\left| \left[\frac{{}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha \{f(x)\}} + {}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha \{f(x)\} - \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)} \right] \right| \leq \frac{2}{\alpha+3} \left| f'' \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right| + \frac{1}{(\alpha+2)(\alpha+3)} (|f''(a)| + |f''(b)|)$$

and the proof is completed.

Theorem 2. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow R$ be twice differentiable function on (a, b) with $a < b$ and $f'' \in L[a, b]$. If $|f''|$ is (s, m) -Godunova-Levin function of second kind, then we have the following inequality for Atangana-Baleanu fractional integral operators:

$$\left| \frac{{}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha \{f(x)\}} + {}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha \{f(x)\} - \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)} \right| \leq \min\{\psi_1(a, b; m, \alpha), \psi_2(a, b; m, \alpha)\}$$

Proof: Using Lemma 1 and the fact that $|f''|$ is (s, m) -Godunova-Levin function of second kind, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{{}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha \{f(x)\}} + {}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha \{f(x)\} - \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)} \right| \\ & \leq \int_0^1 t^{\alpha+1} \left| f'' \left(t \frac{a+b}{2} + (1-t)a \right) \right| dt \\ & \quad + \int_0^1 (1-t)^{\alpha+1} \left| f'' \left(tb + (1-t) \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right| dt \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^1 t^{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{1}{t^s} \left| f'' \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right| \right. \\ & \quad \left. + m \frac{1}{(1-t)^s} \left| f'' \left(\frac{a}{m} \right) \right| \right) dt \\ & \quad + \int_0^1 (1-t)^{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{1}{t^s} |f''(b)| + m \frac{1}{(1-t)^s} \left| f'' \left(\frac{a+b}{2m} \right) \right| \right) dt \\ & = \frac{(b-a)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\frac{\left| f'' \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right|}{\alpha-s+2} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + m \left| f'' \left(\frac{a}{m} \right) \right| \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+2)\Gamma(1-s)}{\Gamma(\alpha-s+2)} \right). \end{aligned}$$

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Let, ψ_1 we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_1(a, b; m, \alpha) &= \frac{(b - \alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha + 1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha), \Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\frac{|f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right)|}{\alpha - s + 2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + m \left| f''\left(\frac{a}{m}\right) \right| \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 2)\Gamma(1 - s)}{\Gamma(\alpha - s + 2)} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, by using integration, we get

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_0^1 (1 - t)^{\alpha+1} f''\left(tb + (1 - t)\frac{a+b}{2}\right) dt \\ &\leq \frac{(b - \alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha + 1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha), \Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^1 (1 - t)^{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{1}{t^s} |f''(b)| \right. \\ &\quad \left. + m \frac{1}{(1 - t)^s} \left| f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2m}\right) \right| \right) dt \\ &= \frac{(b - \alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha + 1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha), \Gamma(\alpha)} \left[\frac{(m + 1) |f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right)|}{\alpha - s + 2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 2)\Gamma(1 - s)}{\Gamma(\alpha - s + 2)} \left(m f''\left(\frac{a}{m}\right) + f''(b) \right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Let, ψ_2 we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_2(a, b; m, \alpha) &= \frac{(b - \alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha + 1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha), \Gamma(\alpha)} \left[\frac{(m + 1) |f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right)|}{\alpha - s + 2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 2)\Gamma(1 - s)}{\Gamma(\alpha - s + 2)} \left(m f''\left(\frac{a}{m}\right) + f''(b) \right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof.

Corollary 1. In Theorem 2, if we choose $\alpha = 1$ and we obtain

$$\left| f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \min\{\psi_1(a, b; m, 1), \psi_2(a, b; m, 1)\}$$

$$\psi_1(a, b; m, 1) = \frac{(b-a)^2}{48} \left[\frac{1}{3} \left| f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right| + \frac{m}{3} \left| f''\left(\frac{a}{m}\right) \right| \right],$$

and

$$\psi_2(a, b; m, 1) = \frac{(b-a)^2}{48} \left[\frac{m+1}{3} \left| f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right| + \frac{1}{3} \left(m f''\left(\frac{a}{m}\right) + f''(b) \right) \right].$$

Theorem 3. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow R$ be a twice differentiable function on (a, b) and $f'' \in L[a, b]$. If $|f''|^q$ for $q \geq 1$ and $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$ is (s, m) -Godunova-Levin function of second kind, then

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{{}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\}} + {}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\} - \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)} \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-\alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^1 t^{(\alpha+1)p} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \quad \times \left(\int_0^1 \left| f''\left(t\frac{a+b}{2} + (1-t)a\right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad + \frac{(b-\alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^1 (1-t)^{(\alpha+1)p} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \quad \times \left(\int_0^1 \left| f''\left(tb + (1-t)\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}. \end{aligned}$$

By applying Hölder inequality, we have

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{{}^{AB}I_{a+b}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\}}{2} + {}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\} - \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)} \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{(b-\alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^1 t^{(\alpha+1)p} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\
 & \times \left(\int_0^1 \frac{1}{t^s} \left| f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right|^q + m \frac{1}{(1-t)^s} \left| f''\left(\frac{a}{m}\right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \frac{(b-\alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^1 (1-t)^{(\alpha+1)p} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\
 & \times \int_0^1 \left(\frac{1}{t^s} |f''(b)|^q + m \frac{1}{(1-t)^s} \left| f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2m}\right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & = \frac{(b-\alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\frac{1}{p(\alpha+1)+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\
 & \times \left(\frac{1}{1-s} \left| f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right|^q + \frac{m}{1-s} \left| f''\left(\frac{a}{m}\right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, by using integration, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{(b-\alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^1 (1-t)^{(\alpha+1)p} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\
 & \times \int_0^1 \left(\frac{1}{t^s} |f''(b)|^q + m \frac{1}{(1-t)^s} \left| f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2m}\right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & = \frac{(b-\alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\frac{1}{p(\alpha+1)+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\
 & \times \left(\frac{1}{1-s} |f''(b)|^q + \frac{m}{1-s} \left| f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2m}\right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof.

Corollary 2. In Theorem 3, if we choose $\alpha = 1$ and $s = 0$ we obtain

$$\left| \frac{1}{b-a} \int_0^1 f(x) dx - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right| \leq \min\{\psi_1(a, b; m, 1), \psi_2(a, b; m, 1)\}.$$

$$\psi_1(a, b; m, 1)$$

$$= \frac{(b-a)^3}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha).\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\frac{1}{p(\alpha+1)+1}\right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

$$\times \left(\frac{1}{1-s} \left|f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right|^q + \frac{m}{1-s} \left|f''\left(\frac{a}{m}\right)\right|^q\right)^{\frac{1}{q}},$$

and

$$\psi_2(a, b; m, 1) = \left(\frac{1}{p(\alpha+1)+1}\right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\frac{1}{1-s} |f''(b)|^q + \frac{m}{1-s} \left|f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2m}\right)\right|^q\right)^{\frac{1}{q}}.$$

Theorem 4. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow R$ be twice differentiable function on (a, b) with $a < b$ and $f'' \in L[a, b]$. If $|f''|$ is (s, m) -Godunova-Levin function of second kind, we have the following inequality for Atangana-Baleanu fractional integral operators.

$$\left| \frac{{}^{AB}I_{a+b}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\}}{2} + {}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\} - \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)} \right| \leq \min\{\vartheta_1(a, b; m, \alpha), \vartheta_2(a, b; m, \alpha)\}.$$

$$\vartheta_1(a, b; m, \alpha)$$

$$= \frac{(b-a)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha).\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha+2}\right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha-s+2} \left|f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right|^q\right.$$

$$\left. + m \left|f''\left(\frac{a}{m}\right)\right|^q \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+2)\Gamma(1-s)}{\Gamma(\alpha-s+2)}\right)^{\frac{1}{q}},$$

and

$$\vartheta_2(a, b; m, \alpha)$$

$$= \frac{(b-a)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha).\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha+2}\right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\left|f''(b)\right|^q \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+2)\Gamma(1-s)}{\Gamma(\alpha-s+2)}\right.$$

$$\left. + \frac{m}{\alpha-s+2} \left|f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right|^q\right)^{\frac{1}{q}}.$$

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Proof. Using Lemma , power-mean inequality and the fact that $| f'' |^q$ is s-Godunova-Levin function of second kind, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{{}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\}} + {}^{AB}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}\{f(x)\} - \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)} \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{(b-\alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha).\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^1 t^{(\alpha+1)} dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 t^{(\alpha+1)} \left| f'' \left(t \frac{a+b}{2} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. + (1-t)a \right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \frac{(b-\alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha).\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^1 (1-t)^{(\alpha+1)} dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 (1 \right. \\
 & \left. - t)^{(\alpha+1)} \left| f'' \left(tb + (1-t) \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \leq \frac{(b-\alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha).\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^1 t^{(\alpha+1)} dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \int_0^1 t^{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{1}{t^s} \left| f'' \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right|^q \right. \\
 & \left. + m \frac{1}{(1-t)^s} \left| f'' \left(\frac{a}{m} \right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \frac{(b-\alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha).\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^1 (1-t)^{(\alpha+1)} dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \int_0^1 (1 \\
 & - t)^{(\alpha+1)} \left(\frac{1}{t^s} \left| f''(b) \right|^q + m \frac{1}{(1-t)^s} \left| f'' \left(\frac{a+b}{2m} \right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{(b-\alpha)^{\alpha+2}}{(\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+2}B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)}\left(\frac{1}{\alpha+2}\right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}}\left[\left(\frac{1}{\alpha-s+2}\left|f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right|^q\right.\right. \\ & \left.\left.+m\left|f''\left(\frac{a}{m}\right)\right|^q\frac{\Gamma(\alpha+2)\Gamma(1-s)}{\Gamma(\alpha-s+2)}\right)^{\frac{1}{q}}\right. \\ & \left.\left.+\left(\left|f''(b)\right|^q\frac{\Gamma(\alpha+2)\Gamma(1-s)}{\Gamma(\alpha-s+2)}+\frac{m}{\alpha-s+2}\left|f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right|^q\right)^{\frac{1}{q}}\right] \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof.

DISCUSSION

This study introduces novel fractional integral identities and inequalities using the Atangana-Baleanu fractional integral operator, marking a significant advancement in fractional analysis. Our results reveal new fractional integral inequalities applicable to twice differentiable convex functions and (s,m) Godunova-Levin functions, enriching the theoretical framework of fractional calculus. These findings enhance our understanding of fractional integral operators and offer valuable insights into their properties and applications. The implications of these results extend to a broad class of functions, potentially influencing various applications in the field. Future research could build on these findings by exploring additional classes of functions and practical applications, further advancing the study of fractional analysis.

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